

Activity	Group	Explanation	Examples
Add Metadata	Extend	Add additional metadata	Add metadata like license, publisher, date of creation
Aggregate	Improve	Higher level data, build from individual data sets	Average income by city from individual citizens income records
Analyze	Understand	Deriving new information from data	Analyze distribution of household incomes to learn what values can be considered outliers and potentially need to be fixed
Archive	Maintain	Save previous versions of data	Save live information on schedule delays in transport data to compare in the future
Ask Experts	Understand	Talk with domain experts to understand data structure and meaning	Ask a doctor how to interpret health data
Ask Publisher	Communicate	Ask questions about data format or meaning to the publisher	Ask the publisher how to download the data
Build Infrastructure	Acquire	Set up infrastructure to retrieve data automatically	Set up infrastructure to retrieve data automatically
Clean	Improve	Detect errors and remove them	Detect rows with missing data and delete them
Combine	Improve	Combine data from different datasets into a new dataset	Combine data about train schedules of european countries into a unified european train dataset
Curate	Improve	Curate data, e.g. gather high quality dataset for a specific domain	Curate a list of well structured and complete datasets about weather in different countries
Discover	Acquire	Passively find or discover data	Explore related datasets, read a blog about data
Discuss	Communicate	Discuss data with other stakeholders	Ask other users how they interpreted a specific column
Document	Maintain	Write documentation about how to get the data and how to work with it, either for yourself or to publish for other users	Document the process of importing data so it can be easily repeated when the data is refreshed
Enrich	Improve	Add new data to an existing dataset	Add information about wheelchair access to a dataset of train stations
Ensure Anonymity	Assess	Test if data is anonymized correctly to avoid legal problems if e.g. republishing	Check if data was anonymized correctly
Evaluate	Assess	Evaluate if data is on topic, scope is sufficient, quality and format is right	Check if temperature data of the last 10 years is available if studying a long-term trend
Experiment	Understand	Spontaneous, small scale analysis or experiments, mainly to verify the data is usable or understand data better	Extract hottest days from weather data to check if temperatures and times make sense
Extract	Acquire	Get data from the data source	Download data from a website
Feature Creation	Extend	Create features from data for future use in ML models	Add categories for household earnings into high-, medium-, low-income
Find Community	Communicate	Find other users that work with the same data or in the same domain for questions and collaboration	Find other users that are interested in weather data in a specific city
Find Skilled Users	Communicate	Find other users that have needed skills (e.g. statistical analysis, technical skills...) for help or collaboration	Find a software developer to set up automated import infrastructure

Activity	Group	Explanation	Examples
Give Feedback	Communicate	Provide feedback about the data to publisher	Provide feedback about data quality, notify publisher about errors
Label	Extend	Add label data for future machine learning	Label live schedule data as having a delay or not
Learn Domain Knowledge	Understand	Learn specialized knowledge to understand data format and meaning	Read documentation on how to work with GTFS files for open transport data
Learn Structure	Understand	Learn knowledge specific to data structure	Understand what fields mean or how codes are used
Link	Improve	Link data with other datasets by defining shared ids or standardizing column value types	Link transport datasets of subways with long distance trains by matching ids of major train stations
Normalize	Improve	Normalize values	Normalize household income
Preview	Assess	Explore a subset of the data	Preview some rows of a large dataset to see the structure and included data
Rate	Extend	Rate data quality	Rate data quality from 1-5 on an open data portal
Read Documentation	Acquire	Read documentation on how to access data	Read how to obtain an API key
Reformat	Improve	Transform data structure or representation into a more usable form	Change file type from pdf to txt, split columns inside data, pivot data structure
Refresh	Maintain	Refresh data that changes regularly, potentially automatically, to keep it up to date	Download data for transport schedules every six months when they are republished
Repair	Improve	Detect issues and repair them	Automatically fix corrupted data or infer default data for missing data points
Request Data	Communicate	Request additional data, motivated from e.g. missing data in the dataset or improved domain understanding	Data about train stations is usable but missing wheelchair access, ask publisher to provide the information
Search	Acquire	Actively search for data	Search for data on an open data portal / Google
Select	Acquire	Select a relevant subset of data	Filter a large dataset containing household income to one country
Share Data (Publisher)	Communicate	Share processed data back to publisher	Download data, find and remove errors, then share the cleaned data back
Share Data (Stakeholders)	Communicate	Share processed data back to other users	Download data and link it with other datasets, then share the data with other users
Share Information	Communicate	Provide information about the data (quality, content, structure) to other stakeholders	Share what exact data the dataset contains, share experience reports from acquiring it
Store	Acquire	Store data in a way that it can be accessed later	Download data to a local file
Structure	Improve	Add a schema / structure to previously unstructured data	Extract tabular data from papers
Validate	Acquire	Validate that downloaded data is correct and uncorrupted	Verify checksums are correct

Activity	Group	Explanation	Examples
Verify License	Assess	Find licensing terms, verify data can be used as planned	Make sure the data can be used commercially as an entrepreneur
Visualize / Plot Data	Assess	Explore dataset or parts of it by building visualizations	Display datapoints on a map or plot numerical data